

Basic principles of catalysis

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Abstract

This article describes the basic principles of catalysis through the three elements of catalysis. The three elements of catalysis: positive and negative pairs, catalytic disturbance, and total background disturbance.

1. Regarding the three elements of catalysis.

Positive and negative pairs

Based on the most fundamental principles of physics, only positive and negative charges have an attractive effect. Any form of chemical bond is essentially achieved in a positive negative pairing mode, with the difference being the manifestation. Please note that 'positive and negative pairs' is an abstract model here, rather than a literal charge separation.

Catalytic disturbance

The role of a catalyst is to provide a disturbance that reduces the stability of positive and negative pairs.

Total background disturbance

All chemical bonds are subject to some background influence, including their own molecular kinetic energy and various external influences. They can be regarded as the background influence on the stability of chemical bonds as a whole, named as the sum of background perturbations, and their numerical value is called the background perturbation threshold.

2. The relationship between the three.

Catalytic perturbation reduces the stability of positive and negative pairs, and when the stability is below the background perturbation threshold, the chemical bond is broken. Figure 1

Fig.1

3. Regarding the three characteristics of catalysts: activity, selectivity, and stability.

These three characteristics are actually different combinations of catalytic elements.

Activity

Stability residual value = Stability of positive and negative pairs - Background disturbance threshold - Catalytic disturbance. The smaller the stability residual value, the greater the activity. Figure 2

Selectiveness

The stability of the substrate and catalyst combination is greater than the background disturbance threshold, and the stability of other intermediate combinations is less than the background disturbance threshold. Figure 3

Selectivity mainly includes two elements: energy matching and shape matching. Energy matching is to achieve effective catalytic disturbance, which is a rigid requirement. Shape matching is a non rigid requirement, which can be tolerated even if the shape is not completely matched. For example, some enzymes can still catalyze efficiently when their shapes are not exactly matched.

Stability

The stability of the catalyst itself is greater than the background disturbance threshold, and the stability of the catalyst and product combination is less than the background disturbance threshold.

Discussion

Based on the three element model, each part can be quantified and calculated, so there is reason to believe that the three element model can efficiently design catalysts. The model is still far from perfect, but it is worth improving, and this requires the participation of everyone.